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● ***Euryarthrum petramarketae* sp. nov. from Binh Thuan, Vietnam (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae: Cerambycinae: Prothemini)**

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Abstract: A new species of the genus *Euryarthrum* Blanchard, 1845 is described from Binh Thuan Province in Vietnam. *Euryarthrum petramarketae* sp. nov. is described, illustrated and compared with similar species.

Keywords: longhorn beetles, new species, Oriental Region, taxonomy

● **越南平顺一天牛新种——佩玛长棒天牛（鞘翅目：天牛科：天牛亚科：长跗天牛族）**

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摘要：本文描记一个产自越南平顺省的长棒天牛属新种——佩玛长棒天牛 *Euryarthrum petramarketae* sp. nov.。本文图示了该新种并与相似种进行了对比。

关键词：天牛，新种，东洋区，分类

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● Introduction

Blanchard (1845) described the genus *Euryarthrum*, belonging to the tribe Prothemini, with the type species *Euryarthrum albocinctum* Blanchard, 1845 from Singapore. *Euryarthrum* contains twenty known species and three subspecies (Tavakilian & Chevillotte 2025).

In the present paper, a new species of the genus *Euryarthrum* is described from material which was collected by local collector in Binh Thuan Province, Vietnam, in June 2024. Description of the following new species is provided: *Euryarthrum petramarketae* **sp. nov.** from Binh Thuan Province, Vietnam. Habitus and male genitalia are illustrated. The new species is compared to the similar species *E. apicefasciatum* Hüdelpohl, 1988, *E. assimile* Yoshitake & Niisato, 2010 and *E. rubati* Fuchs, 1966.

● Material and methods

Observation and photography. The habitus of specimens and genitalia photographs were taken using a Canon MP-E 65mm/2.8 1–5× Macro lens on bellows attached to a Canon EOS 550D camera. Each photograph was taken as several partially focused images and afterwards composed in the Helicon Focus 8.2.18 Pro software. The photographs were modified using Adobe Photoshop CC.

Specimens examined including type materials are deposited in the following collection: **CPV** (collection of Petr Viktora, Kutná Hora, Czech Republic). A slash (/) separates data in different lines on locality and determination labels.

● Taxonomy

Genus *Euryarthrum* Blanchard, 1845

Type species: *Euryarthrum albocinctum* Blanchard, 1845

Euryarthrum petramarketae **sp. nov.**

<https://zoobank.org/6D1A104F-1872-4598-B666-531AA05E38BC>

Fig. 1

Type locality. Vietnam, Binh Thuan, Dong Tien.

Type material. Holotype (♂): 'Vietnam' / 'Binh Thuan' / 'Dong Tien' / '6/2024', (CPV).

Description. Habitus of male holotype as in Fig. 1a. Body from reddish brown to black, elongate, relatively robust, largely almost glabrous, partly with pubescence. Body length from mandibles to elytral apex 14.1 mm, the widest at humeral part of elytra (4.0 mm), 3.52 times longer than wide.

Head black, long and narrow, distinctly narrowing anteriorly, posterior half matte, anterior half distinctly glossy, the widest across the eyes, distinctly narrower than pronotum at the widest point. Dorsal surface almost glabrous, with distinct, coarse irregular granulation and microgranulation/micropunctuation (anterior half largely with irregular granulation and irregular large-sized punctation, glossy), disc with a few long, erect colourless setae, eyes and antennal insertions with short pale setation on edges. Interspace between antennal insertions narrow, antennal insertions with raised edges, prolonged on inner side (tips rounded). Eyes blackish, finely faceted, strongly emarginate (not divided into two parts). Clypeus glossy, from pale ochre yellow to blackish brown, labrum semi-matte, brown with shallow large-sized irregular punctation, microwrinkled, with long goldenish setation in edges. Mandibles large, distinct and massive, blackish, glossy, with distinct, irregular large-sized granulation/punctuation, with a few goldenish setae on edges.

Maxillary palpus pale reddish brown, semi-glossy, microwrinkled, partly with indistinct, short goldenish setation. Palpomeres short, last palpomere the longest and the largest, cylindrical, distinctly widened apically with rounded apical margin.

FIGURE 1. *Euryarthrum petramarketae* sp. nov.: A male holotype B male genitalia.

FIGURE 2. *Euryarthrum apicefasciatum* Hüdepohl, 1988: male from Malaysia (Perak), (CPV).

Antennae with 11 antennomeres, long (almost reaching elytral apical margin, as in Fig. 1a), distinct, significantly extended in apical half. Antennomeres reddish brown (antennomeres 1–5 darker, antennomeres 1–2 largely blackish, antennomere 3 partly blackish), semi-matte. Antennal scape widened apically with distinct edge in apex, antennomeres 2–4 rounded apically, antennomeres 6–11 distinctly wider and serrate, antennomere 11 with distinct tooth on edge in approximately 3/4 of length, narrowing apically to rounded tip. Antennomeres with short, indistinct yellowish pubescence (very sparse on antennomeres 1–5, denser in antennomeres 6–11). Antennomeres 1–3 with coarse irregular granulation, antennomeres 4–5 with less coarse irregular granulation, antennomeres 6–11 microwrinkled. Antennomere 2 the shortest, antennomere 11 the longest. Ratios of relative lengths of antennomeres 1–11 equal to: 0.98 : 0.22 : 1.00 : 0.58 : 0.62 : 0.74 : 0.78 : 0.68 : 0.64 : 0.57 : 1.18.

Pronotum black, robust, convex, narrower than elytra at humeri. Pronotum the narrowest at anterior margin, 1.13 times longer than wide at base and as long as wide at the widest point (approximately half of pronotal length). Lateral margins arcuate, anterior margin and base slightly widened in middle (as in Fig. 1a), pronotal disc convex, rounded. Dorsal surface almost glabrous, matte (glossy only in edges of granules), with distinct, coarse irregular granulation and microgranulation/micropunctuation, with distinct depression in basal margin, covered by dense, recumbent white pubescence. Pronotal disc with a few erect colourless setae in basal half.

Scutellum small, black, matte, triangular, glabrous.

Elytra almost parallel, shortly narrowing apically, 8.6 mm long and 4.0 mm wide (2.15 times longer than wide), black, matte, with spots of dense, recumbent white pubescence (each elytron with interrupted transverse band in basal third and preapical transverse band) (as in Fig. 1a). Elytral surface almost glabrous, with distinct, coarse irregular granulation forming irregular reticulation, surface between cells microwrinkled. Elytral disc flat, humera and place under scutellum elevated, lateral margins very distinct, with a narrow raised edge. Elytral apex with regularly rounded lateral angles, sutural angles with short, elevated spine. Elytral epipleura very distinct, undulate, black, matte, microwrinkled, the widest at apical part, lower edge of epipleural apex distinctly prolonged into wide spine, spines are visible even from overall dorsal view (as in Fig. 1a).

Pygidium blackish brown with narrowly brown apical margin, with shallow irregular punctation, microwrinkled, covered by short, sparse pale pubescence, margin slightly narrowly elevated, with longer yellowish setation, apex regularly rounded.

Legs semi-glossy, reddish brown, with dense, shallow, small-sized irregular punctation, covered by short, relatively sparse pale pubescence (inner side of femora largely glabrous) and goldenish setation (the densest on protibiae). Femora undulate club-shaped, tibiae widened apically, distinctly curved. Metafemora and metatibiae very long, distinctly longer than pro- and mesofemora and pro- and mesotibiae. Tarsi reddish brown, pro- and mesotarsi wide, metatarsi narrow (the longest including claws), with dense small-sized punctation, covered by whitish pubescence and denser goldenish setation. Protibial spurs short and narrow, mesotibial spurs slightly longer, narrow, curved, metatibial spurs the longest, narrow, distinct, curved. Metatarsomere 1 strongly flattened, 1.4 times longer than metatarsomeres 2 and 3 combined.

Ventral side of body largely black, coxae blackish brown, ventrites from dark brown to blackish brown. Ventral surface with dense small-sized punctation, microwrinkled. Mesepisternum, metepisternum and metasternum with spots/stripes of dense white pubescence at apical parts, ventrites with stripes of dense white pubescence at apical margins, rest of surface with sparse shiny pubescence, prosternum partly with relatively long shiny setation. Tergite 8 distinctly curved at a right angle, triangular apical part forms a distinctive raised thorn.

Genitalia as in Fig. 1b.

Female. Unknown.

Differential diagnosis. The most similar species (based on a transverse preapical stripe of pale pubescence on the elytra) are *Euryarthrum apicefasciatum* Hüdelpohl, 1988 (Fig. 2), described from peninsular Malaysia (Cameron Highlands), and *Euryarthrum assimile* Yoshitake & Niisato, 2010, described from the Malaysian state of Sabah on

the island of Borneo.

Euryarthrum petramarketae **sp. nov.** (based on comparison of males) differs from the species *E. apicefasciatum* (Fig. 2) mainly by the different shape of pronotum (more arcuate lateral margins in *E. apicefasciatum*), the different colouring (antennae reddish brown except blackish antennomeres 1–2, legs completely reddish brown in *E. petramarketae*, while antennae reddish brown except black antennomeres 1–5, legs completely black in *E. apicefasciatum*), the lower edge of epipleural apex prolonged into shorter wide spine than in *E. apicefasciatum*, the pubescence stripes on elytra snow white and wide (yellowish and distinctly narrower in *E. apicefasciatum*), the distinctly longer and narrower protarsi, the distinctly longer antennae with more elongate antennomere 11, the longer and more curved metatibial spurs, and the longer metatarsi (as in Figs. 1a and 2).

Euryarthrum petramarketae **sp. nov.** (based on comparison of males) differs from the species *E. assimile* mainly by the different colouring (antennae reddish brown except blackish antennomeres 1–2, legs completely reddish brown in *E. petramarketae*, while antennae and legs completely black in *E. assimile*), the pubescence stripes on elytra snow white and wide (pale yellowish and narrower in *E. assimile*), and the more curved metatibial spurs.

Euryarthrum rubati Fuchs, 1966, described from Lam Dong province in Vietnam, has reddish brown legs, just like *Euryarthrum petramarketae* **sp. nov.**, but it belongs to a different group of *Euryarthrum* species with only one transverse stripe of light pubescence in the middle part of the elytra.

Etymology. The species is dedicated to my daughter Petra and wife Markéta.

Distribution. Vietnam (Binh Thuan).

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● Additional information

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